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A Systematic Review of Literatures on Dominating Factors Influencing Work-Life Balance of Female Employees

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Abstract:

Employment and family are two indispensable parts of the lives of career women. Working women typically manage two jobs continuously at home and the workplace, making it difficult to find equilibrium in their personal and professional lives in this rapidly changing world. This paper attempts to identify the key elements influencing employed women's work-life balance (WLB) by reviewing previous literature findings. The results of the investigation suggest that regardless of the industry, country, or culture of an employee, organizational support, work demands, time demands, gender perception, role demands, and support from spouse and families are among the common factors that either improve or impede their ability to strike equilibrium between professional and personal life. These findings will give an important lead in promotional policies and decision-making for policymakers and organizations.

Keywords: work-life balance, WLB, working women, female employees, review, gender, role

1. INTRODUCTION

The employment of women is becoming a worldwide phenomenon. Their increased participation in the workforce has resulted in significant economic benefits for businesses and nations. The position of women in the global economy is rapidly shifting from traditional to modernized cultures. Financial pressures drive women to enter the workforce, which has gradually developed their state of mind. Previously dependent on men, women have taken steps to address economic challenges. They now understand that in order to be recognized and provide for their families, they must work just as hard as men. (Marlow, 2002). Therefore, they enter the workplace to be independent, financially assist their families, and live a stress-free lifestyle.

The Bureau of Labor Statistics has reported steady increase in the number of women joining the labor market driven by financial necessity and the pursuit of a higher quality of life. Women's financial empowerment worldwide has shaped a revolutionary scale during the past five decades. For example, the female-to-male earnings ratio increased dramatically from 73% to 84% from 2000 to 2022 (Statista 2024), portraying the vital role of women in today's economy. Career women have also experienced advantages such as engaging in choice-making, improving living standards, higher social status, and boosting their confidence level (Cleveland et al. 2000).

Due to caregiving obligations for children and other family members, women's engagement in the labor market and working hours are typically more restricted than men's. Additionally, women encounter challenges such as pay fairness, the "glass ceiling" effect, and issues specific to their gender at work, like lack of flexibility in

managing childcare and family obligations (**Greenhaus & Powell 2003; Reynolds 2005**). According to **Sherwani (1984)**, one of the major issues women encounter while trying to reconcile job and family life is having to play double roles, which causes friction and disputes due to her social system. Work-life balance (WLB) benefits employed women. WLB is commonly understood to be a person's level of equally satisfied involvement, or "fit," among the various responsibilities in their life. A person can accomplish personal and professional goals with an efficient WLB (**Dubey et al., 2010**).

Studies conducted over the last thirty years have shown that WLB has drawn a great deal of care and consideration from academics, labor organizations, and employers (**Dex and Bond 2003; Felstead et al. 2002; Taylor 2001**). However, no thorough analysis of empirical research on WLB and associated dominant elements affecting it has been carried out. Thus, it is imperative to carry out context-specific research in order to gain a deeper insight of work-life difficulties as well as the contextual elements that influence the work-life experiences of female employees. This knowledge is essential for management scholars to establish a theoretical explanation of work-life study and assist HR managers in designing policies that enhance worker's welfare and company output.

This paper reviews and conceptually explains the main factors influencing working women's WLB. Selected articles on the WLB for female workers from 2010 to 2024 were reviewed using secondary data.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Women in workforce

Women first entered the workforce in the 1970s. The notion of shared breadwinning was first suggested by **Nock (2001)**, where 40%–50% of income is contributed by each spouse, coined MEDS (Marriage of Equally Dependent Spouses). **Caudron (2001)** reported that the percentage of career women has increased over time due to their competence, ability to pursue challenges, creative ideas, unique opinions, and desire to be recognized and given a voice in society.

Female workforce involvement is a significant aspect of their overall contribution to the labor market. However, due to organizational demands, men and women are frequently required to put in long hours in their jobs, resulting in work overload and lengthy, unstructured workdays. These pressures are experienced differently by each gender. Employed women often want to balance multiple roles, including those of loving and caring mothers, wives, responsible daughters-in-law, and professional executives (**Chincholkar & Krishna 2012**). For this reason, women seek more fascinating and multifaceted professions with supporting co-workers and where job content and socio-emotional aspects are valued. This leads to greater job satisfaction for women, positively impacting their family life (**Imran et al. 2011**). Conversely, men are more likely to look for financial rewards, employment autonomy, independence, status, and recognition in the workplace. As a result, they frequently take less time to attend to their familial responsibilities.

Despite constitutional rights ensuring gender equality and equal opportunity, societal norms still enforce different expectations of behavior for men and women, even in the workplace. **Vasumathi (2018)** found in her research that women made up a small percentage of all workers in Indian cities and towns, with the bulk of them holding low-status positions. Another survey on Indian working women was carried out by **Suchitra and Rajasekhar (2006)**, who discovered that unskilled women employed in the construction industry received lower pay than their similar unskilled male counterparts.

A consistent increase in the number of women entering the workforce has gradually diminished traditional gender notions, fostering a more equal perception of men and women (**Botkin 2000**). Although the participation of women in Pakistan's workforce is marked by social disapproval, their involvement in the labor force has increased with slow progress (**FBS 2020–2021**). Women in India have moved from being restricted to non-

managerial, subordinate, or low-profile roles to holding positions in almost every field of work today, expanding their duties and responsibilities to society and their families (Mathew & Panchanatham 2009).

Despite the surge of women joining the labor force, balancing job expectations with their personal and family obligations is challenging. Peeters et al. (2005) indicate the incompatibility of professional and family pressures frequently causes an imbalance. Therefore, the concept of WLB and its implications are crucial areas of investigation as more women join the labor industry.

2.2 Multidimensional roles of women

Women usually have to tackle several responsibilities simultaneously, each with its own demands, rather than seamlessly transitioning from one task to another (Kopp et al. 1993). She is a spouse, caregiver, mother, and daughter, manages regular housework, and provides community and societal services at the same time (Mathew & Panchanatham 2011). Moreover, she has to attend to her personal needs and health, which are frequently ignored due to time constraints and duty overload. The social role theory states that other members become unhappy when someone fails to fulfill their tasks and responsibilities (Eagly and Wood 2011). Consequently, if a woman cannot effectively perform her numerous tasks, her career and family responsibilities may suffer. Multitasking can have mixed effects on women's psychological well-being. Some women juggling diverse roles report better physical and psychological wellness, appreciating physical stamina, energy, self-esteem, motivation, and a sense of control (Doress Wortes 1994). Yet, handling diverse roles can also negatively affect women's health, causing issues like weight gain, sleeplessness, overindulgence in food, and back pain (Hughes 1994).

Figure 1: Multidimensional roles of women

2.3 The cause of the imbalance

An unbalanced relationship arises between a working mother's professional and personal lives when she excels in one field but stumbles in another that is equally important. (Anwar et al., 2013). A working mother who aims to attain a successful career at the same time bears a more outstanding obligation to fulfill the role of a mother and take care of her developing child. Both tasks are complex and need parallel attention; prioritizing one without overlooking the other is a challenging effort. Vasumathi (2018) mentioned that changes in work culture have exacerbated work-life conflicts, primarily due to growing workload, development in IT, constant connectivity, information overload, and the demand for quality service. These factors lead to long working

hours, overtime, and tight deadlines, negatively affecting personal life and causing an unbalanced lifestyle between work and home. Work-life conflicts often stem from the dual pressures of family caregiving and work intensification, leading to unhappiness, sadness, and poor physical health (Cooke & Jing 2009). In Indian society, women's time and energy are significantly strained due to their evolving roles as employees with distinct occupational identities (Adya 2008). A national survey on work and life-related problems in Canada discovered that one in every four Canadians claimed job duties conflicted with home responsibilities (Duxbury & Higgins, 2003). Employees experience an imbalance due to role conflicts, employment pressures, various responsibilities, domestic commitments, childcare, superiors' and family members' attitudes, and competition. This imbalance can lead to absence from work, higher stress levels and low focus at work. As more families become nuclear or dual-income, the question of WLB becomes increasingly crucial. (Rekha & Asha 2024).

2.4 Concept of Work-life Balance

Work-life balance refers to preserving a healthy balance between a person's professional and personal lives. In the UK, the phrase "work-life balance" was primarily used to refer to the art of balancing one's personal and professional lives in the late 1970s. Extensive research on this topic has led to a wide range of definitions, theoretical frameworks, measurement methods, and an understanding of its determinants and consequences, resulting in a complex body of literature.

The term "work-life balance" appears to have multiple definitions. Marks and MacDermid (1996) provided an early formal definition, describing it as the desire to be fully involved in each role within one's overall role arrangement, treating each role and role companion with devotion and concern. Greenhaus et al. (2003) offered an alternative definition, emphasizing equal time and participation in various roles: 'Work-life balance involves engaging in multiple roles with approximately equal levels of attention, time, involvement, or commitment'. They also highlighted the importance of balanced fulfillment across all aspects of life, defining it as equally satisfying responsibilities in both work and non-work areas. Additionally, Greenhaus et al. (2003) stressed balanced engagement and fulfillment across life domains, describing WLB as managing time and mental energy to yield high satisfaction from both areas. In modern days, the concept of WLB has increasingly emphasized family aspects. Nath and Patra (2010) defined it as setting suitable priorities between career and ambition and family, relaxation, and religious growth. This semantic shift acknowledges that there are also a lot of non-work responsibilities other than childcare and that they can be related to various unpaid pursuits or obligations such as education, sports activities, travel, charitable work, personal growth, recreation, or eldercare. Kundnani and Mehta (2015) define WLB as effectively operating the equilibrium between work and personal life, ensuring that an individual remains profitable and competitive at work while also leading a healthy and fulfilling social life. Modern researchers have observed work-life balance as a mental state, encompassing a broad concept that involves prioritizing "life" aspects like physical wellbeing, satisfaction, relaxation, family, and religious growth with "work" aspects like profession and ambition (Rekha & Asha 2024). In its most expansive definition, "work-life balance" is described as the satisfactory integration of a person's various life roles. From the above discussion, it is crucial to realize that WLB refers to achieving a fulfilling degree of participation or 'fit' among several responsibilities in one's life domain, not equally dividing time between paid work and unpaid roles. While definitions may differ, work-life balance generally pertains to maintaining a harmonious equilibrium between the time and effort dedicated to professional and personal conduct, ensuring complete life congruence (Clarke et al., 2004).

2.5 Importance of Work-life balance

Work-life balance received little consideration before the early years of the twenty-first century. Western European and Anglo-Saxon countries have emphasized WLB the most (Chandra 2012), followed by Eastern European countries (Shaffer et al. 2011). Progressively, the significance of studying the work-family domains has come to the attention of researchers from different countries (Poelmans et al. 2005). The Asia-Pacific region has only just begun to pay attention to the WLB in recent years (Verma et al. 2009; Cooke & Jing

2009; Hassan 2010;). Rao & India (2010) have noted that work often dominates one's life, highlighting the need to address work-life imbalance. Nowadays, workers spend a more significant portion of their time on their jobs compared to the past. Guest (2002) asserts that extended workdays and time constraints at the workplace lead to elevated stress levels, extending work into weekends and evenings, which reduces quality time with family. Work-home conflict occurs from the incompatibility of the demands placed on families and the workplace due to overwork. These conditions raise concerns about wellness and WLB concerns. Many companies and academics nowadays view WLB as a crucial area of concern. Balancing job and family responsibilities, important components of an individual's existence, requires considerable time and energy. This balance profoundly affects employees' physical and mental wellbeing (Schultheiss 2006). Individuals and organizations promoting work-life balance have observed its benefits. According to Karatepe & Bekteshi (2008), one of the organization's key responsibilities is fostering WLB, as it enhances inspiration and productivity. Numerous studies have proven that work-life balance promotes organizational performance, enhances job satisfaction, and strengthens commitment within an organization (Allen et al., 2013). Gallinsky's (2005) study suggested that a model of WLB is important for boosting employee loyalty and dedication to the company, as well as improving their mental health. A review of different research has concluded that companies that offer balanced WLB schemes see increases in employee satisfaction and productive devotion to the company (Shaikh et al. 2019). Achieving the right balance positively affects career, family, and personal fulfillment. This makes it a crucial field for research in quality-of-life studies, organizational behavior, and HRM.

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

We conducted this comprehensive review in accordance with standard practices for review writing (Short 2009). After discussing the research topic on working women and work-life balance, we looked into the fundamental causes and came up with the review question: 'What are the primary factors that contribute to balance or imbalance in the work-life situation of employed women?' By posing this query, we could pinpoint the main problems we were trying to comprehend in the literature on work-life balance and how it has affected the lives of working women. We also saw how research on the topic has addressed these problems.

To lay the groundwork for the subsequent literature review, we conducted a content analysis, integrating both quantitative and qualitative aspects to assess descriptive and content criteria. We conducted an extensive search on scholarly databases including Web of Science and Google Scholar, primarily focusing on peer-reviewed journals, conceptual and review papers, and experimental studies that employed explicit measures of work-life dimensions. To ensure validity, we collected data from various research papers presented at seminars and published in national and international journals with peer reviews. Due to concerns about their quality, we excluded non-refereed sources, such as these, reports, journal articles from unknown publishers, and book chapters.

We categorized publications based on their contents and time periods while searching for data. The material selection for the review was conducted qualitatively and intensively, focusing on the years 2010 to 2024. To prepare the foundation for the subsequent literature review, we searched keywords such as work-life balance, factors influencing WLB, review on working women etc. A total of 15 studies were included in this review. The studies in our sample utilized data from developing countries, such as India, Pakistan, and Nigeria, as well as developed nations, like the USA, China, and various countries in Europe. We reviewed each article and discussed the expanding body of knowledge, extracting from it the key factors that influenced the WLB of employees. Six key themes were identified, namely gender equality, marital status, parental status, organizational culture, and role engagement. These themes formed the basis of the review criteria. Based on the key themes, we developed a conceptual framework.

Figure 2: The methodological approach of the research

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Content Analysis

Over the past 15 years, several excellent literatures on work-life balance have been published. Various literary works addressed distinct topics. We attempted to select the most significant ones. This review paper aims to offer a thorough analysis of national and international peer-reviewed journals relating to WLB. We have focused on the key elements influencing women employees' work-life balance. The table below gives an overview of the studies and highlights important findings from each

Table 1: Critical Factors Impacting Work-Life Balance

Serial No.	Authors	Dominating Factors Influencing WLB	Key Findings
1.	S. S. Shaikh et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee engagement • Organizational support • Personality 	This study examined the variables influencing Pakistani women employed by NGOs in balancing their home and professional lives. Organizational support, employee engagement, and personality explained 73% of the variance, with organizational backing making the highest contribution and personality the lowest.
2.	S. Rehman & M.A. Roomi (2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job experience • Family & spouse support • Time management • Gender perceptions 	The work-life balance of Pakistani women entrepreneurs was examined in this study. The results indicate that the most significant challenges to achieving WLB include a lack of sufficient time, gender bias, social and cultural norms, and family responsibilities.
3.	R. V. Mathew & N. Panchanatham (2011)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role demand • Dependent care • Time management • Social support 	This study's findings indicate that time management, support networks, and WLB are positively correlated. The study also reveals that health risks could result from role demand and dependent care issues.
4.	Rekha & Asha (2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work-family conflict • Role demand • Work stress • Child & dependent care 	This article explores how female employees integrate their professional and personal lives. It identifies four factors influencing their work-life balance and suggests that women skillfully manage their balance and responsibilities to maximize their potential across all four spheres of life.
5.	A. Vasumathi (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managerial support • Organizational time demand • Work demand • Telecommuting 	This review article addresses the WLB of female employees, covering its importance, theories, determinants, facilitators, coping strategies, and outcomes. It underscores the need for working

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-worker support • Competitive environment • Work stress • Work-family conflict • Gender perceptions 	women to receive support from family members, organizations, and government policies to tackle their challenges and balance work and personal life.
6.	Sirgy & Lee (2017)	<p><u>Personal factors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work engagement • Job value • Family engagement • Conscientiousness • Anxiety-proneness • Coping strategy • Individualism • Power distance • Traditional male roles • Risk aversion <p><u>Organizational factors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work demand • Time demand • Job autonomy • Role confusion • Flexible Working Practices • Part-time employment • Childcare support • Parental support services/breastfeeding assistance • Senior care support • Employee health and wellness scheme • Low irritability • WLB policies • Social support 	This review article identifies various personal and organizational factors that precede work-life balance and explains their impact on achieving it.
7.	H. Le et. al. (2020)	<p><u>Work-related factors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-worker support • Managerial support • Work demand • Job autonomy • Work stress • Work characteristics • Organizational embeddedness • WLB policies <p><u>Non-work-related factors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family & spouse support • Social Support • Child & dependent care • Role demand • Personality traits • Parental demand • Time management 	This systematic review presents an overview of Asia's work-life interface, offering valuable insights into how cultural, economic, and institutional factors shape employee perceptions. It highlights the need for multilevel research, methodological improvement, and an expansion of work-life frameworks throughout Asia.
8.	K.A. Goyal & A.A. Babel (2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Working Practices • Time Management • Telecommuting • Part-time job 	This study examines the concerns and challenges of WLB in the banking sector in India. According to the study, WLB policies and programs are an investment that enhances productivity, reduces absenteeism, improves customer service, promotes better health, enables flexible working conditions, and fosters a satisfied and motivated workforce, thereby achieving a balance between work and life.

9.	A. Babatunde (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender perception • Role demand 	The following study reveals that macro-environmental factors such as corruption, high unemployment rates, poverty, inflation, and patriarchy contribute to work-life conflict (WLC) among women in Nigeria's service sectors. These women often accept WLC as a part of life, and the coping strategies they adopt tend to repress conflict instead of removing stress.
10.	K. Beddoes & A. L. Pawley (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Management • Child & dependent care • Gender perceptions • Role demand 	This study finds that female faculty in STEM fields are underrepresented in the United States. It highlights how difficulties connected to families affect female faculty more than those related to male faculty. The study connects these gender inequalities in STEM departments to the discourse surrounding choice.
11.	T. Lunau et. at. (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management • WLB policies 	This study demonstrates that health issues are linked to a poor WLB affecting both men and women across 27 European countries. WLB varies by country and is influenced by labor laws, working hours and welfare state policies. Scandinavia is considered to have the best overall work-life balance, indicating that it has better WLB policies.
12.	A. Gregory, S. Milner & J. Windebank, (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative support 	This article raises broader questions about the policies that support employees' work-life balance during austerity and economic downturn. The authors claim that legal support for work-life balance can help alleviate structural inequities.
13.	J. M. Haar et. al. (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individualism/collectivism cultures • Gender egalitarianism 	The results of the SEM analysis of this research showed that, in various cultural contexts, the correlations between WLB and job satisfaction, life satisfaction, anxiety, and depression were mediated by gender egalitarianism and individualism/collectivism.
14.	H. Chung & T. van der Lippe (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Employment Practices 	The findings of this study suggest that flexible work schedules can enhance family dynamics and promote a better work-life balance. However, because women are frequently expected to take on more household obligations while working flexibly, they are more likely to suffer unfavourable career outcomes from flexible working hours.
15.	V. Chandra (2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender perceptions • Coping strategies • Flexible working practices • WLB policies 	This study examined and contrasted the views on work-life balance held by Eastern and Western cultures. Gender socialization and coping strategies played a major role in WLB in Asian companies, while American companies focused on flexible working practices.

4.2 SUMMARY OF MAJOR THEMES

Family and work are two intertwined facets of life. Balancing their expectations can be rather tough, often leading to work-life conflict (WLC). The above content analysis of the work-life interface identified some general themes that influence WLB. Hence, these themes predict how WLB influences an employee's life—and work domains.

4.2.1 Gender perceptions

Work and family duties are prioritized differently by men and women. Women encounter more career obstacles than men (**Lyness and Thompson 2000**). Sirgy (2017) argues that employees in masculine cultures value competitive accomplishments in the workplace, which leads to high work-to-family conflict. In contrast, employees in feminine cultures favor care and family relationships over work, causing family-to-work conflict. Men's advancement is facilitated by marriage and children, whereas they hamper women's advancement. Thus, the strategies for balancing work and family responsibilities differ between genders. While women often make more compromises at work to satisfy their household responsibilities, men typically make greater sacrifices at home. (**Jennings and McDougald 2007**). Moreover, career decisions made by male spouses are given preference over those made by female partners. (**Beddoes & Pawley 2014**) Therefore, without the support of their families and spouses, professional married women might not thrive (**Rehman & Roomi 2012**).

4.2.2 Marital Status

In comparison, married people place a higher value on their personal lives than single people do. It is often difficult for employees with families to create lines between their personal and work lives, which can harm both domains. **Md-Sidin et al. (2008)** think there is more work-life conflict among married persons than unmarried people.

4.2.3 Parental Status

Parental status has a substantial influence on WLB. Having children in a family significantly impacts an individual's WLB experiences (**Tausig and Fenwick 2001**). WLB is higher for dual-earner couples without children, but the perceived balance is substantially lower for married couples with kids. (**Tausig and Fenwick 2001**). **Lawton and Tulkin (2010)** found that having children in the home is the main aspect of family structure that increases work-life conflict. Consequently, to avoid conflict, women with children were much less committed to their jobs than women without children (**Rekha & Asha 2024**). Some work-life policies, such as paternity leave, are specially designed for males to create a broader sharing of duties between men and women (**Vasumathi 2018**). However, in other cultures, pregnancy and individuals who take parental leave are perceived negatively (**Beddoes & Pawley 2014**).

4.2.4 Personal traits

Previous studies on the link between personality and work-life balance indicates that personality qualities influence performance at work. (**Cain 2015; Barrick, Mount & Li 2013**). Characteristics like Calmness, Sociability, Cooperativeness, Open-mindedness, and Reliability define one's personality. It has been proposed that a person's level of WLB difficulties is dominated by certain factors, such as accountability, loyalty, extravertive personality, openness to experience, and the need and want to be with family (**Bekker et al., 2010**). Individuals with intense negative feelings tend to have more unfavorable interactions with work and family. (**Bekker et al., 2010**). However, **Shaikh et al. (2019)** discovered that career women's work-life balance is less influenced by their personality features.

4.2.5 Organizational culture

A broad spectrum of organizational cultural traits, such as features of the job and the type of support they provide, employee engagement, managerial support, time demand, work demand, and flexible working practices, also perform a major function in WLB. The work culture mirrors the organizational culture and the extent of support offered to employees for managing work and family obligations. This may involve WLB programs, family-supportive policies, and an environment of trust and empathy. (**Goyal & Babel 2015**). Studies

have shown that WLB is affected by various job characteristics, such as deadline pressure, occupational demands, role confusion, decision-making authority, and flexible work arrangements. Organizational support, including a flexible work environment and necessary off-time for family and other necessities, can assist employees in striking a better work-life balance. According to numerous researchers, women's work-life balance is positively impacted by organizational support (McCarty et al. 2013; Nishaat 2017). Various organizational programs, such as flexible scheduling, shortened work hours, childcare services, caregiver assistance, health and wellness plans, family leave provisions, family resources, and workplace social support, are designed to help employees better manage their work and life responsibilities (Chandra 2012).

4.2.6 Role engagement

A crucial aspect of achieving work-life balance is active participation in professional and personal roles. According to research, people dedicated to multiple responsibilities in diverse life domains can attain work-life balance (Sirgy & Lee 2018). A healthy work-life balance requires substantial time and engagement in both work and family roles, whereas an unhealthy balance happens when individuals do not dedicate sufficient time or energy to either area. Individuals who attain work-life balance participate in multiple duties and find fulfillment by effectively allocating their time and energy across these important areas of their lives. (Kalliath & Brough 2008). Specifically, individuals engaged in various life areas are likely to gain increased influence, status, resources, and emotional fulfillment from their diverse roles. Engaged employees produce a meaningful work environment, eventually contributing to maintaining work-life balance (Shaufeli & Bakker, 2010; Munn, 2013; Bakker & Oerlmans, 2012;). Multiple roles provide individuals with role advantages, overall status protection, assets for status improvement, and self-enrichment. Thus, those deeply engaged in non-work and work life have access to resources and opportunities that are unavailable to those who concentrate solely on work.

5. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

After going through the content analysis, we discovered some important elements that directly affect women employees' work-life balance. For our conceptual framework development, we have selected the factors that have a more significant impact and have been identified by various scholars from different perspectives of WLB. Moreover, these factors can influence women employees' WLB regardless of industry, country and culture. The common work-related variables that we have found in the literature were organizational support, work demand, and time demand. In contrast, non-work-related common factors were gender perception, role demand and spouse and family support. The fitting balance of these factors the appropriate balance of these components improves performance in roles, resulting in happiness among women employees that spreads across their work and life domains. Findings suggest that minimal Work-Life Conflict occurs when the maximum level of WLB is received.

Figure 3: Conceptual framework of common factors affecting WLB

6. CONCLUSION

Work-life balance is now more important than ever due to changes in values brought about by changes in the workforce. Women often must maintain two full-time jobs at home and work, making work-life balance particularly crucial. Working mothers frequently face misconceptions and shifting perspectives as they transition from working women to working mothers. The overall study largely contributes to scholarly understanding of the major aspects that can be found to influence women's work-life balance. The study's practical implications highlight the urgent need for socially conscious and accountable employers and government to raise awareness of the laws and concerns impacting feasible WLB arrangements. Our study suggests that if working women receive the support they need from their families, employers, and government policies, they will be able to address their various problems and maintain a work-life balance. This will enable them to lead peaceful lives and pave the way for the nation's rapid growth and development.

6.1 Limitations of the study

This study reviewed a few kinds of literature for time constraints. We have attempted to address the most important factors impacting the work-life balance of women employees despite the abundance of content, making it extremely difficult to comprehend and synthesize the study thoroughly. Given the need for organizations to maintain healthy WLB for employees, there is a scope for more holistic and multilevel analysis in the future.

REFERENCES

- Adya M., (2008). Women at Work: Differences in IT Career Experiences and Perceptions between *South Asian and American Women*. *Human Resource Management*, 47(3):601-635.
- Allen, T. D., Johnson, R. C., Kiburz, K. M., & Shockley, K. M., (2013). Work-family conflict and flexible work arrangements: deconstructing flexibility. *Personnel Psychology*, 66, 345–376.
- Anwar, J., Hasnu, S.A.F. and Janjua, S.Y., (2013). 'Work life balance: what organizations should do to create balance', *World Applied Sciences Journal*, Vol. 24, No. 10, pp.1348–1354.
- Babatunde A., (2013). 'An exploratory study of work-life balance in Nigeria: Employees' perspectives of coping with the role conflicts', *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*

- Bakker, A.B., & Oerlemans, W.G.M., (2012). Subjective wellbeing in organizations. In K.S. Camerson, J.E. Dutton, & R.E. Quinn (Eds). *Positive organizational scholarship* (pp. 178-189). San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers, Inc.
- Barrick, M.R., Mount, M.K., & Li, N., (2013). The theory of purposeful work behavior: The role of personality, higher order goals, and job characteristics. *Academy of Management Review*, 38(1), 132-153.
- Beddoes K. & Pawley A.L., (2014). 'Different people have different priorities': work-family balance, gender, and the discourse of choice, *Studies in Higher Education*, 39:9, 1573-1585, DOI: 10.1080/03075079.2013.801432
- Bekker, M., Willemse, J. and De Goeij, J., (2010). 'The role of individual differences in particular autonomy-connectedness in women's and men's work-family balance', *Women & Health*, Vol. 50, No. 3, pp.241–261.
- Botkin, D.R., (2000). 'Changing marriage role expectations: 1961–1996', *Sex Roles: A Journal of Research*, Vol. 42, No. 9, pp.933–943.
- Cain, L. N., (2015). Examining the factors that impact work-life balance for executive chefs. *William F. Harrah College of Hotel Administration, The Graduate College. University of Nevada, Las Vegas*,
- Caudron, S., (2001). "The myth of job happiness", *Workforce-Costa Mesa*, Vol. 80 No. 4, pp. 32-7.
- Chandra V., (2012). Work-life balance: eastern and western perspectives. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23:5, 1040-1056, DOI:10.1080/09585192.2012.651339
- Chandra, V., (2012). 'Work-life balance: eastern and western perspectives', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 23, No. 5, pp.1040–1056.
- Chincholkar, S. and Krishna, N., (2012). 'Work- family conflict of married women business executives in Mumbai', *SIES Journal of Management*, Vol. 8, No. 2, p.63.
- Chung H. & Van der Lippe T. (2018). 'Flexible Working, Work-Life Balance, and Gender Equality: Introduction'. *Social Indicators Research* 151:365–381 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-018-2025-x>
- Clarke, M.C., Koch, L.C. and Hill, EJ, (2004). 'The work-family interface: differentiating balance and fit', *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp.121–140.
- Cleveland, J.N., Stockdale, M., Murphy, K.R. and Gutek, B.A., (2000). *Women and Men in Organizations: Sex and Gender Issues at Work*, pp.30–44, Psychology Press, Mahwah, NJ.
- Cooke FL, Jing X., (2009). Work Life Balance in China: Sources of Conflicts and Coping Strategies. *NHRD Network Journal*, 2(3):18-28.
- Cooke, F. and Jing, X., (2009). 'Work-life balance in China: sources of conflicts and coping strategies', *NHRD Network Journal (Work-Life Balance Special Issue)*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp.18–28.
- Dex, S. and Bond, S., (2005). 'Measuring work-life balance and its covariates', *Work Employment Society*, Vol. 19, No. 3, pp.627–637.
- Doress-Wortes PB., (1994). Adding elder care to women's multiple roles: A critical review of the caregiver stress and multiple roles literature. *Sex Roles*, 31:597-613.
- Dubey, S., Saxena, R. and Bajpai, N., (2010). 'Work life balance: Can women be both bearer and manager', *Journal of Engineering, Science and Management Education*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp.15–21.

- Duxbury L, Higgins C., (2003).The 2001 National Work Life Conflict Study, Final Report. *Public Health Agency of Canada*.
- Eagly, A.H. and Wood, W., (2011). "Social role theory", in Van Lange, P.A., Kruglanski, A.W. and Higgins, E.T. (Eds), *Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology*, Sage Publications, London, pp. 458-78.
- Federal Bureau of Statistics (FBS) (2020-2021), Labour Force Survey, Statistics Division Karachi: The Manager of Publications, Karachi.
- Felstead, A., Jewson, N., Phizacklea, A. and Walter, S., (2002). 'Opportunities to work at home in the context of work-life balance', *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 12, No. 1, pp.54–76.
- Gallinsky, E., (2005). The changing workforce in the United States: Making work "work" in today's economy. *Inaugural Conference of the International Center of Work and Family, IESE Business School, Barcelona*.
- Goyal K.A. & Babel A.A., (2015). 'Issues and Challenges of Work Life Balance in Banking Industry of India' *Pacific Business Review International*, Vol.: 8, No.5
- Greenhaus, J. H., Collins, K. M., & Shaw, J. D., (2003). The relation between work-family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63, 510–531.
- Greenhaus, J.H. and Powell, G.N., (2006). 'When work and family are allies: a theory of work-family enrichment', *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 31, No. 1, pp.72–92.
- Gregory A., Milner S., Windebank J., (2013)."Work-life balance in times of economic crisis and austerity", *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, Vol. 33, 9/10 pp. 528 – 541
- Haar J.M., Russob M., Suñe A., Ollier-Malaterre A., (2014). 'Outcomes of work–life balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health: A study across seven cultures.' *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 85 361–373
- Hassan, Z., (2010). 'Work-family conflict in Eastern vs. Western countries', *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*, Vol. 17, No. 1, pp.30–49.
- Hughes, D. L., & Galinsky, E. (1994). Gender, job and family conditions, and psychological symptoms. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 18(2), 251-270.
- Imran, M., Ahmad, A., Gomez, S.F. and Ali, M., (2011). 'A study of work environment and employees' performance in Pakistan', *African Journal of Business Management*, Vol. 5, No. 34, pp.13227–13232.
- Jennings, J. and McDougald, M., (2007). 'Work-family interface experiences and coping strategies: implications for entrepreneurship research and practice', *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 32, No. 3, pp.747–760.
- Kalliath, T., & Brough, P., (2008). Work-life balance: a review of the meaning of the balance construct. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 14, 323–327.
- Karatepe, O. M., & Bekteshi, L., (2008). Antecedents and outcomes of work–family facilitation and family–work facilitation among frontline hotel employees. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27, 517–528.
- Kopp, R. G., & Ruzicka, M. F. (1993). Women's multiple roles and psychological well-being. *Psychological Reports*, 72(3_suppl), 1351-1354.

- Kundnani, N. and Mehta, P., (2015). Identifying the Impact of Financial obligations on overall Stress and Work-Life of Bank Employees. *Management*, 6(3), pp.01-09.
- Lawton, L. and Tulkin, D., (2010). 'Work family balance, family structure and family friendly employee programs', Annual Meeting of the Population Association of America, Dallas, Texas, 15 April.
- Le H., Newman A., Menzies J., Zheng C., Fermelis J., (2020). 'Work-life balance in Asia: A systematic review' *Human Resource Management Review*
- Lunau T., Bambra C., Eikemo T.A., Van der Wel K.A., Dragano N., (2014). 'A balancing act? Work-life balance, health and wellbeing in European welfare states. *European Journal of Public Health*, Vol. 24, No. 3, 422-427
- Lyness, K.S. and Thompson, D.E., (2000) 'Climbing the corporate ladder: do female and male executives follow the same route?', *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vo. 85, No. 1, pp.86-101.
- Marks, S. R., & MacDermid, S. M., (1996). Multiple roles and the self: a theory of role balance. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 58, 417-432.
- Marlow, S., (2002). "Women and self-employment: a part of or apart from theoretical construct?" *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 83-91.
- Martins, L., Eddleston, K. and Veiga, J., (2002). 'Moderators of the relationship between work-family conflict and career satisfaction', *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 45, No. 2, pp.399-409.
- Mathew R.V. & Panchanatham N., (2011). 'An exploratory study on the work-life balance of women entrepreneurs in South India, *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 16, No. 2, 77-105
- Mathew, R. V., & Panchanatham, N. (2009). Work life balance issues among the women entrepreneurs in South India. *Emerging entrepreneurial strategies for self-development and skill development*, 46-57.
- Mathew, R.V. and Panchanatham, N., (2011). An exploratory study on the work-life balance of women entrepreneurs in South India. *Asian academy of management journal*, 16(2).
- McCarthy, A., Cleveland, J. N., Hunter, S., Darcy, C., & Grady, G., (2013). Employee work-life balance outcomes in Ireland: A multilevel investigation of supervisory support and perceived organizational support. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(6), 1257-1276.
- Md-Sidin, S., Sambasivan, Mp. and Ismail, I., (2008). 'Relationship between work-family conflict and quality of life', *Journal of Management Psychology*, Vol. 25, No. 1, pp.58-81.
- Munn, S.L., (2013). Unveiling the work-life system: The influence of work-life balance on meaningful work. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 15(4), 401-417.
- Nath, S. and Patra, S., (2010). 'Better work-life balance: strategic business issue', *AIMA Journal of Management*, Vol. 4, No. 1, p.43.
- Nishaat, B. Z. (2017). Achieving work family balance (WFB) among professional working women in Mauritius: A qualitative study. *PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2), 2053-5074.
- Nock, S.L., (2001). "The marriages of equally dependent spouses", *Journal of Family Issues*, Vol. 22 No. 6, pp. 755-75.
- Peeters, M. C. W., Montgemery, J. J., Bakker, A. B. & Schaufeli, W.B., (2005). Balancing work and home: How job and home demands are related to burnout. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 12, 43-61.

- Poelmans, S., O'Driscoll, M. and Beham, B., (2005). 'An overview of international research on the work-family interface', *Work and Family: An International Research Perspective*, pp.3–46, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahwah, NJ.
- Rao, T.S. and Indla, V., (2010). 'Work, family or personal life: why not all three?', *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp.295–297.
- Rehman S. & Roomi M.A., (2012). 'Gender and work-life balance: a phenomenological study of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan'. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 209-228
- Rekha, Asha, (2024). Factors affecting work-life balance of working women. *International Journal of Finance and Commerce*, Vol.6, No.1, pp 1-6
- Reynolds, J., (2005). 'In the face of conflict: work-life conflict and desired work hour adjustments', *Journal of Marriage and Family*, Vol. 67, No. 5, pp.1313–1331.
- Schaufeli, W.B., & Bakker, A.B., (2010). Defining and measuring work engagement: Bringing clarity to the concept. In A.B. Bakker, & M.P. Leiter (Eds). *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research*. New York, NY: Psychology Press.
- Shaffer, M.A., Joplin, J.R. and Hsu, Y-S., (2011). 'Expanding the boundaries of work-family research: a review and agenda for future research', *International Journal of Cross-Cultural Management*, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp.221–268.
- Shaikh, S.S., Shah, S.A.S., Katpar, N.K. and Shah, S.K.B., (2019). Factors affecting work-life balance of women working in NGOs of Pakistan. *The Women-Annual Research Journal of Gender Studies*, 11(11).
- Sherwani, M. (1984). Why more women entering work force. *Yojana*, 28(10), 7.
- Short, J., (2009). The art of writing a review article. *Journal of Management*, 35(6), 1312–1317.
- Sirgy, M.J. and Lee, D.J., (2018). Work-life balance: An integrative review. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 13, pp.229-254.
- Statista, 2024. US. female to male earnings ratio 1990-2022. [Online], available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/203459/female-to-male-earnings-ratio-of-workers-in-the-us/#:~:text=The%20ratio%20indicates%20that%20a,%2DU%2DRS%20adjusted%20dollars>.
- Suchitra, J.Y. and Rajasekhar, D., (2006). 'One-Size-does-not-fit-all: employment insecurity of unorganized workers in Karnataka', *The Indian Journal of Labor Economics*, Vol. 49, No. 3, pp.455–473.
- Tausig, M. and Fenwick, R., (2001). 'Unbinding time: alternate work schedules and work-life balance', *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, Vol. 22, No. 2, pp.101–120.
- Taylor, R., (2001). *The Future of Work Life Balance*, ESRC Future of Work Program Seminar Series, Swindon.
- Vasumathi, A., (2018). Work life balance of women employees: a literature review. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 29(1), pp.100-146.
- Verma, A., Chang, Y., Kim, H. and Rainboth, S., (2009). 'Realizing the Korean dream for work-family balance: employer policies for sustainable societies', *NHRD Network Journal (Work-Life Balance Special Issue)*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp.29–52.